

CHEMISTRY OF THE RARE-EARTHS. PART V. BASIC NITRATES OF YTTRIUM EARTHS

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Basic nitrates of Yt, Yb and Gd have been studied and each has been shown to give a soluble basic nitrate of the composition $3R_2O_3, 4N_2O_5$. Gadolinium has, in addition, been found to give an insoluble basic salt $GdONO_3$ similar to those for cerium earth and bismuth as expected from its position in the series.

Yttrium, as has been shown by James and Pratt (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 32, 873) gives only one basic nitrate of the composition $3Y_2O_3, 4N_2O_5, 20H_2O$, soluble in water. Thermometric and conductometric titration curves of yttrium nitrate with caustic soda solution obtained by the present author also reveal the existence of only one basic nitrate of the above composition. To see whether this is a common characteristic of the elements of the yttrium group, the basic nitrate of ytterbium has been studied. The conductometric titration of ytterbium nitrate with caustic soda solution gives a curve analogous to that of yttrium nitrate with caustic soda, showing only one basic nitrate $3Yb_2O_3, 4N_2O_5$ of similar composition, which therefore appears to be characteristic of the elements of the yttrium group.

While studying gadolinium and its compounds Sarkar (*Ann. chim.*, 1927, 8, 239) isolated a basic nitrate of the composition $3Gd_2O_3, 4N_2O_5, 20H_2O$ soluble in water and perfectly analogous to that of yttrium. It is to be expected, however, from its position in the "serial order" of the rare earths, that gadolinium should possess properties characteristic of both cerium and yttrium groups, for example,

(i) Gadolinium gives an acid tartrate of the composition $HGd(C_4H_4O_6)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ similar to the corresponding salt of bismuth.

(ii) The basic nitrate $3Gd_2O_3, 4N_2O_5, 20H_2O$ is analogous to the corresponding salt of yttrium.

(iii) The addition product of gadolinium nitrate with antipyrine of the composition $Gd(NO_3)_3, 3C_{11}H_{13}ON_2$ resembles those of the cerium group.

(iv) The compound of gadolinium nitrate with hexamethylene tetramine has the composition $Gd(NO_3)_3 \cdot 2C_6H_{12}N_4, 10H_2O$ analogous to those of the yttrium group elements.

(v) Gadolinium platincyanide crystallises with 18 molecules of water of crystallisation, characteristic of the cerium group—those of the yttrium group crystallise with 21 molecules of water; its colour, however, is cherry-red with beautiful green fluorescence characteristic of yttrium group. Those of cerium group have yellow colour with blue fluorescence.

A detailed study of the basic nitrates of gadolinium has therefore been made by the present author to see whether there exists also any basic nitrate analogous to those of cerium group elements. Conductometric titration curve of gadolinium nitrate with caustic soda solution as well as the thermal decomposition curve of gadolinium nitrate with increasing temperature have revealed the existence of two basic nitrates—the first having the composition $3Gd_2O_3, 4N_2O_5$ previously described by Sarkar (*loc. cit.*) analogous to the corresponding salt of yttrium, soluble in water, and second of the composition $GdONO_3$ not previously described and analogous to that of bismuth and cerium earths, insoluble in water.

E X P E R I M E N T A I

Purification of Yttrium Nitrate.—Yttrium nitrate available in the market supplied by Kahlbaum was used as the starting material. The mean equivalent weight has been determined and found to be 114.5. It contains besides yttrium small quantities of other yttrium earths like Dy, Ho and Er and also a little of the cerium earths. Separation of the latter is best assured by the known method of separation with sodium sulphate. For this purpose finely powdered anhydrous sodium sulphate is added to the solution of the nitrate or chloride while hot under stirring, till a portion of the test solution does not show any absorption band of Nd. The solution is freed from alkali salts by precipitation with ammonia then redissolving in nitric or hydrochloric acid. The remaining yttrium earths having absorption, viz. Dy, Ho and Er is removed by the ferricyanide method of Prandtl (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1938, 238, 328). For this purpose, to a not too dilute neutral or neutralised solution was added concentrated warm potassium ferricyanide under stirring from which after allowing to stand for some time, the absorption lines of Ho and Er completely disappeared from the solution. From the filtrate of the ferricyanide, yttrium was precipitated with caustic soda as hydroxide, washed, dissolved in HCl or HNO₃ and the concentrated solution examined spectroscopically for absorption. The still remaining Yt earths containing Dy, Ho, and Er were removed by treating again with K₃FeCy₆ and remaining cerium earths by precipitation with sodium sulphate. For final purification, the differential decomposition of the nitrate was utilised. For this purpose, the nitrate was heated in a porcelain basin at 300° till the mass took a sleeky appearance. It was then extracted with hot water and allowed to crystallise, when yttrium was obtained as its basic nitrate in microcrystalline form. The purity of the substance was tested spectroscopically when only mere traces of gadolinium were detected. The purity was further tested by the determination of the atomic weight from the ratio $Y_2(SO_4)_3, 8H_2O : Y_2O_3$ and this has been found to be 89.5.

Purification of the Ytterbium Fraction.—Ytterbium fraction of unknown origin was used as the starting material. It contained besides ytterbium, its neighbours thulium and lutecium and very little of the cerium earths. The latter were removed by precipitation with sodium sulphate. From the filtrate the rare-earth was precipitated twice with ammonia as hydroxide, washed free of alkali salts, dissolved in HCl and precipitated with oxalic acid; the oxalate was then ignited to oxide and the oxide was dissolved in acetic acid to convert it into acetate. The final purification was made according to the method of Marsh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 8). The method consisted in the reduction of $YbAc_3$ with sodium amalgam and subsequent formation of ytterbium amalgam since its neighbours are devoid of amalgam forming power. For this purpose the acetate was dissolved in the least quantity of boiling water and was treated hot with sodium amalgam, the solution was made weakly acid to prevent the formation of hydroxide. The amalgam was then treated with excess of hydrochloric acid and ytterbium precipitated as oxalate and the latter ignited to oxide. The purity of the sample was tested by determination of the atomic weight from the ratio $Yb_2(SO_4)_3, 8H_2O : Yb_2O_3$ and this was found to be 172.5.

Thermometric Titration : Yttrium Nitrate and Caustic Soda.

Experimental arrangements were the same as presented in a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 75).

The solution ($M/10$) of yttrium nitrate (40 c.c.) was taken in the inner flask and caustic soda solution ($2M$) was added from the burette at regular intervals and changes in temperature noted. The differences in temperature were then plotted against the volume of alkali solution added. Here, the curve, unlike those for the elements of the cerium group (*cf.* Part III of this series), shows one break corresponding to $3Y_2O_3$, $4N_2O_5$, where the ratio of the nitrate to alkali is $1:1.667$ corresponding to that of James and Pratt (*loc. cit.*) besides a second one corresponding to the hydroxide $Y(OH)_3$, where the above ratio is $1:3$. Results appear in Fig. 1.

FIG. 3

FIG. 2

FIG. 4

Conductometric Titrations.—All measurements were made at 32° in an electrically-regulated thermostat. $M/50$ -solution of the nitrates and $2M$ solution of alkali were used. Experimental arrangements were the same as given in Part IV of this series (*loc. cit.*).

Yttrium Nitrate and Caustic Soda.—Here a curve was obtained with one break corresponding to $(3Y_2O_3, 4N_2O_5)$ that of James and Pratt (*loc. cit.*) and a second one corresponding to the hydroxide $Y(OH)_3$. Results obtained are very similar to those obtained by the previous physical method (Fig. 2).

Ytterbium Nitrate and Caustic Soda.—A curve, very similar to the previous one, was obtained with one break corresponding to $3Yb_2O_3, 4N_2O_5$ where the ratio of the nitrate to caustic soda is $1:1.67$ besides that for the hydroxide. The results clearly indicate that the above basic nitrate is characteristic of the yttrium group elements which is of a type quite different from the basic nitrates of the cerium group elements (Fig. 3).

Gadolinium Nitrate and Caustic Soda.—The curve obtained in this case reveals three breaks in all as in the case of the cerium earth elements, with this difference that here the first break corresponds to $3Gd_2O_3, 4N_2O_5$ described by Sarkar (*loc. cit.*), the second one to $GdONO_2$ characteristic of those of first series of basic nitrates of cerium earth elements and also bismuth and a third corresponding to the hydroxide $Gd(OH)_3$ (Fig. 4).

Thermal Decomposition of Gadolinium Nitrate.

Experimental arrangements were the same as described in Part IV of this series.

FIG. 5

On plotting the loss in weight of the nitrate of gadolinium against the constant temperatures, a curve is obtained with three steps. The first step corresponds to $(3Gd_2O_3, 4N_2O_5)$ that described by Sarkar (*loc. cit.*); this is formed at 310° and stable up to 320° . The second step corresponds to $GdONO_2$ analogous to the first basic nitrate of the cerium earth elements not previously described. This is formed at 330° and stable up to 350° . {Found: Gd, 66.48; HNO_3 , 26.65; $GdONO_2$ requires Gd, 66.81; HNO_3 , 26.81 per cent}. The third corresponds to Gd_2O_3 (Fig. 5).

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